

MODULES FOR OPEN SEARCH IN MATHEMATICS TEACHING

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Abstract

To create awareness of the interpretation of search results from some frequently used search engines, learning modules on Open Search are developed and possibilities for a sustainable integration into education are examined. In this paper, a learning module addressing the black box behaviour of some search engines is addressed and links to the German curriculum of mathematics in primary and secondary education are elaborated to enable an implementation into regular teaching. The modules are based on fundamental ideas that can be addressed from kindergarten to upper secondary schools within a spiral curriculum.

HOW TO REACH PEOPLE?

Even children can have a great influence on problem awareness and decision making in society. Especially the movement “Friday for Future” shows this high impact. Lessons learnt in school could have an influence on problem awareness in the family and triggered activities that arise from discussions between kids to their parents similar to environmental risk literacy (e. g. waste sorting and use of plastic, see BMU, 2018, [1]). The Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU) in Germany is convinced that children can argue across from their parents and impart action strategies (BMU, 2018, [1], p. 3). This indicates that sustainability education can be very important if the goal is to change the thinking and decision making of generations. Consequently, this strategy could be transferred to other topics like digital media and search literacy.

The JIM study (Feierabend, Rathgeb & Reutter, 2018, [2], p. 35) showed that children and young people use search engines like Google. The search engine Google ranks 6th out of 13 in the survey of children’s and young people’s favourite internet offers. Search engines like Google are used by 85% daily or several times a week. The trend is slightly upwards with a 2% increase from the previous year’s survey (Feierabend et al., 2018, [2], p. 52). Another German study by the “Deutsches Jugendinstitut” (Feil, Gieger & Grobning, 2013, [3]) showed similar results with more than 1200 children and adolescents between 6 and 12 years of age. Children and adolescents primarily used the search engine Google to search the internet, which is also used by their parents to search for information (Feil et al., 2013, [3], p. 7). Only one-third of parents know alternative search engines for children. Furthermore, the study showed that searching with search engines was accompanied by problems: especially searching with keywords and dealing with the search results posed challenges for the children. The children usually only use the first results when displaying hits. In

addition, they mostly did not go to the website displayed, but presumably took the information primarily from the hit display. The study showed another interesting result regarding the periods of use of search engines: the children and young people used the search engines for search queries much more often during school time instead of during leisure time. This again clearly shows that this topic should be addressed in school.

This creates another problem because the curricula are already filled with important content that must not be omitted and in primary school no new school subject is supposed to be created in Germany: the development and acquisition of the necessary competencies for living in a digital world “[...] go far beyond the necessary basic knowledge of informatics and concern all subjects. Therefore, they cannot be assigned to an isolated learning area.” (KMK, 2016, [4], p. 12, translated by the authors). Dealing with digitalisation in the school sector should focus on the “primacy of the pedagogical” (KMK, 2016, [4], p. 51) and the “primacy of subject didactics” (GDM, 2017, [5], p. 41) and must be integrated into pedagogical and subject didactic concepts in which learning is at the forefront (KMK, 2016, [4]; Platz, 2019, [6]).

To implement the topic of Open Search into the school curriculum, fundamental ideas have to be identified and linked directly to the existing curriculum. As the authors work in the field of mathematics education in Germany, this is exemplarily done in this field in this paper.

The fundamental ideas should already be laid down in a child-friendly way in the initial lessons and be taken up again at the further stages of the learning process, i.e., in later grades, and be structurally enriched in the process. In doing so, the fundamental ideas are taken up again and again at different stages, on the one hand at a higher level and on the other hand in a structurally enriched form (Krauthausen, 2018, [7]). According to the spiral principle, these basic concepts and relationships (fundamental ideas) should be dealt with in mathematics lessons in several cycles, each at a different level, using means of representation, language and didactic models appropriate to the developmental stage of the pupils. The knowledge on a learning topic is developed step by step (in a spiral) (Käpnick & Benölken, 2014, [8], p. 54).

In this project, the learning modules are developed using Design Science Research (DSR; e. g. Peffers et al., 2006, [9]; Prediger et al, 2012, [10]). DSR aims to develop and evaluate solutions to problems to codify knowledge about design sciences as design theories. DSR usually involves the creation of an artefact (in our case: learning modules on Open Search in mathematics teaching) and/or a design theory (in our case: design principles for learning modules linking computer science content to mathematics education) to extend and optimise the current state of

practice as well as existing research knowledge (Vaishnavi, 2019, [11]). With this goal in mind, the Dortmund model for subject didactic development research on diagnosis-guided teaching-learning processes for researching and further developing teaching (e.g. Prediger et al, 2012, [10]) is combined with the DSR Methodology Process for researching and further developing information systems research (e.g. Peffers et al., 2006, [9]) to be able to productively use synergy effects of both approaches for developing learning environments on the topic of open search in mathematics teaching. In the following one exemplary learning module in mathematics education is suggested.

PRIMARY EDUCATION

For search engines to be used purposefully, users need to understand how search engines work and are structured. This is also important for a critical examination of the field. In this learning module (called “Black Box”), the non-transparency of some powerful and frequently used search engines is addressed.

Transparent sorting

In the context of search engines, sorting algorithms play an important role (Halavais, 2017, [12]). Starting already in kindergarten, the functionality of such sorting algorithms can be discovered and actively experienced by the children. Bubble Sort, which is because of its slowness rather of didactic importance (Fischer & Hofer, 2011 [13], p. 839), can already be investigated in kindergarten. Sönnerås (2019) [14] (p. 49f) provided kindergarten children (n=6) with the information, that they learn how a search engine works and that they enter data to be processed on the one “end” and receive sorted data at the other “end”. Rods of different lengths are prepared and the children are asked to pick one and to choose a position on a line (drawn on the floor), where they want to stand first (drawn rectangles can be used for marking the different positions on the line, the number of rectangles corresponds to the number of children). Then the functionality of the flow chart is described: Starting on the left side, the two children who are standing next to each other are supposed to compare the length of their bars. The child with the longer bar should step right, the child with the shorter bar should step left. (Older children might need to help the younger children to get the sorting right). When the child on the right side is reached, the sorting starts again on the left side. After several steps, the sorting is finished and the children put the bars on the floor in front of them to see if it worked. If the order is not correct, a concrete error search can be done with the children. Sönnerås (2019) [14] reports, that the children had doubts about whether the correct sorting was just a coincidence and whether it would work on the next run. They repeated the experiment and started in other rectangles and with other rods, but the result was the same. The children wondered if this would also work with other things instead of the bars. They sorted

themselves by size, among other things, and saw that it also worked. This inductive testing convinced them, that the algorithm would always work. The basis of this activity is measuring, in more detail: direct comparison. This activity promotes competencies in the field of geometry and measuring and sizes (sorting geometric figures according to properties through comparing the lengths of the bars, e. g. KMK, 2004, [15] p. 10 & 11). The direct comparison picks up on previous experiences of the children of ordering and comparing and stimulates a conscious examination of the concepts of relation (“... is as long as ...”; “... is longer as ...”, etc.) through actions. Without these basic experiences in each size range, children cannot build an understanding of the equivalence and order relation in that range (Franke & Ruwisch, 2010, [16], p. 185f). Related to sorting algorithms, the direct comparison is connected with sorting and ordering from the smallest to the largest. In this process, the transitivity of the order relation becomes clear: if bar A is longer than bar B and bar B is longer than bar C, then bar A is longer than bar C. Even though transitivity related to lengths of bars is mastered by almost all children at the beginning of the first school year in primary school, difficulties can arise with weak children in early teaching, and that this requires special attention. The transitivity underlying the order relation, which manifests itself on the children’s level of activity in the fact that they not only compare pairs but can also carry out a ranking (seriation) of several objects, represents an essential aspect of the size concept and measurement concept. However, there is no simple correspondence between action, concept and verbal description for the children (Franke & Ruwisch, 2010, [16]). Through such sorting tasks, process-related competencies can be promoted like communicating (especially working on tasks together, making and keeping agreements) and arguing (especially when checking the sorting process on correctness and finding and correcting errors) (e. g. KMK, 2004, [15] p. 8). Besides Bubble Sort, Insertion Sort and Sorting Networks can be investigated (Quiring-Tegeder, 2016, [17]).

Following this “computer science unplugged” learning environments, “searching as a game” (Menzel, 1978, [18] p. 151ff) can be implemented in primary school using the Scratch programming environment. Schwätzer (2018) [19] describes the approach of constructive programming from the point of view of mathematics didactics and presents some tried and tested examples of lessons in primary school using the Scratch programming environment, including arithmetic and geometry. The subject matter is addressed on three levels:

- (1) exploring with paper and pencil,
- (2) creating a programme flowchart
- (3) independently dealing with code structures.
- In addition, Schwätzer (2018) [19] emphasises the important step of returning to the mathematical content (e. g. by working on mathematical questions about the programme or questioning the sense of using the created programme).

In the learning environment “guessing numbers” Schwätzer (2018, [19], p. 50ff) two problem variations can be investigated and programmed with Scratch:

- (1) the computer “thinks up” a number and gives hints and the child in front of the computer guesses;
- (2) the child in front of the computer thinks up a number, remembers this number and gives feedback to the computer, if the guessed number is too big or too small or if it is the right number. The computer uses the “trick” of always reducing the search spaces by “guessing” exactly the middle number of the search space by forming the new search space from the old one by cutting off the part that is no longer relevant (obtained from the information “too big” or “too small”, i.e. whether it is above or below the middle number) (see also https://pikasmifiles/uploads/images/Spielanleitung_Mister%20X.pdf).

With this game among others understanding of number relations and the sorting of numbers by size (KMK, 2004, [15], p. 9) can be promoted as well as systematic sampling as a problem-solving method (KMK, 2004, [15], p. 7).

Intransparent sorting

In the described learning environments, the supposed sorting order was given (lengths of bars with the relation “... is longer as ...”, cardinal numbers with the relation “... is bigger as ...”) and each involved learner agreed to these orders naturally (because of the order relations on this sets). Especially in the initially described computer science unplugged learning environments, the children might start to ask themselves, which other properties instead of length can be used to sort (e. g. weight, etc.) which could also lead to discussions when the decision for the “right” order is not clear (already in kindergarten: Sönnerräs, 2019, [14], p. 50).

In the next step, objects or even the children themselves could be sorted by the teacher or another child in a certain (maybe even random) order and the children make assumptions about the sorting criteria and find arguments (KMK, 2004, [15], p. 8) for their assumption. As a basis for such sorting profiles can be used. Such profiles could be generated for the whole school class or several school classes and in this way, the pupils collect and afterwards structure and present data in tables, charts and diagrams (competence data, frequency and probability, KMK, 2004, [15], p. 11). If e. g. the question “Which drinking chocolate do you like most?” is asked (e.g. to collect information for the school kiosk) and a ranking of drinking chocolates starting with the most popular (e.g. drinking chocolate A) is done which could represent the search results for the investigated group of children (that could be given to the school kiosk to provide the children with the drinking chocolate that is statistically liked by most of the children in the investigated group). Then the question could be asked: “What would happen if the school kiosk would have a contract with a drinking chocolate provider, whose drinking chocolate (drinking chocolate B) is not liked by most of the children?” as the starting point for a discussion about issues (e. g. economic interests) that could influence a ranking. Furthermore, some children (especially those whose favourite drinking chocolate is not the one liked by most of the children) could perceive the procedure as unfair. In the next task, the option-selection is not binary (like – not like), but fuzzy: The children are supposed to place themselves on a line on the floor where the starting point is “I do absolutely not like” and the endpoint is “I like very much”. With a certain question like “Do you like drinking chocolate C”? Then the children are asked to place themselves on the line. Then a first ranked search result can be assigned based on their position on the line, e. g. as visualized in figure 1:

Figure 1: Example for an assignment of the first search result

This way the assignment of search results based on user profiling can be made experienceable by the children. The children can discuss now, how the assignment was done, what other options there could have been and that the search results individually differ if a search engine uses such procedures.

SECONDARY EDUCATION

Adapting the example to secondary education in schools probability theory and stochastics is a relevant topic in the curriculum. For search engines the ranking is a key element to present the results of the search in a specific order. Learners need to understand how the ranking of search results have an impact on the visibility of results to society and therefore which educational content has an impact on societal changes, risk literacy and awareness. The link

between ranking in search engines and probability theory applied to the visibility of search results is a key to understand the basic principles of search engines. This is also important for a learning module, that addresses ranking in a non-transparent way and how the weights on the search results are assigned, which induces up-ranking and down-ranking of specific results and in turn the visibility of those results in society.

Manual ranking

In the context of search engines, we start with a specific content (e.g., plastic waste and plastic bottles used for soft drinks) with four different internet resources:

- One states that plastic bottles have less weight, need less energy for production and during the transport process than glass bottles and therefore plastic bottles are more environmentally friendly than glass bottles (Stefanini, Borghesi, Ronzano & Vignali, 2021, [20]).
- The next resource is referring to the recycling of the plastic waste in concrete and (Hassani, 2005, [21]) focuses on recycling in comparison to avoiding plastic waste.
- The third source focuses on plastic mitigation and therefore suggests eliminating plastic bottles (Jia, Evans & Linden, 2019, [22]) and switching to alternatives, such as glass bottles.
- The fourth statement addresses microplastics in food chains (Zarfl, 2011, [22]) and how microplastics may have an impact on food safety (World Health Organization (WHO), 2019, [23]).

Curriculum Integration

Integration into the curriculum beyond mathematics education is possible by addressing the same issue in social subjects in schools, by transferring the issue of plastic waste to elections, and by making the specific arguments of political parties visible to the public. A sound problem solving takes multiple views, scientific results from different disciplines, minorities of society and humanitarian side effects into account when decision making is performed. If search results are ranked according to personal preferences of search engines that reflect personal preferences in the ranking violates that principles of decision making based on multiple criteria and neutral point of view (NPOV). A neutral point of view is difficult to achieve even if the NPOV principle is explicitly addressed e.g. Wikipedia's NPOV rules (Matei, 2011, [24]). The main topic may be regarded also as generic for education in school to train critical thinking and encourage the learner to perform evidence-based decision making and being risk literate about the consequence of living in a search bubble in which only the preferences of the own attitudes are communicated to the learner. So going back to the plastic waste example the task for upper secondary students is to search for peer-reviewed articles on the topic and create a manual ranking according to the results and define the criteria in which the articles are ranked. The

students should assign weights to all the search results. Finally, they should discuss which criteria are reflecting personal interest in specific views of the topic and which criteria could be used to perform a more preference independent ranking of the search results.

Ranking and visibility

Now we accept that the assignment of weights to the search result is not transparent to the public. The learner should address the link between ranking and visibility in the context of stochastic and probability theory especially addressed in lower secondary grades as a topic of the curriculum (Schupp, 1982, [25]) starting with a random ranking of search results over three or more visible pages on a computer defined as static HTML pages. These static pages of search results that contain the real links of the internet sources can be ordered according to a specific content by the students. The results in a specific order are presented to other learners who are requested to create a summary of a specific topic. All results will have the same header but have different links of real search results mapped to the header. The intended result would be that learners who receive a particular designed order of search results will produce a different summary of the topic than another group of learners who receive a different order. The learners know that the results are real results of a search engine, but the header has the same topic for all search results e.g. "microplastics, plastic bottle, food chain".

The learning objective is that ordering and ranking of results have an impact on the public opinion derived from the search results. Students should be able to explain what a bias in content delivery is and how it can be generated by an intransparent ranking of search results. The second step is to quantify that approach within the stochastic. The learners should identify a non-Laplace probability distribution on the search results. Assume we have n search results and the click statistics of learners on which of the search results from the list was clicked. Because the learners are exposed to random orders of search results the click statistic of the learner show how ranking creates a preference to use first results at first. If they find suitable answers for their search query they may stop without looking at later ones presented e.g. at the very end of the results. Applied to the context of plastic waste the students will quantitatively analyse the search results they have looked at in more detail and calculate simple probability distributions. Discrete stochastic analysis of non-Laplace probability distributions is required for page rank. Going back to the curriculum consideration in mathematics education, it is possible to link the topic of search engines to probability theory and stochastic without introducing a new topic into the curriculum of lower and upper secondary schools.

CONCLUSION

This paper addresses the possibility to assign a learning module about Open Search addressing the Black Box behaviour of some frequently used search engines which can be linked to the standard curriculum in primary schools and secondary schools in mathematics education in Germany. Stochastic and combinatoric content was identified as a link to the standard curriculum. In lower secondary schools non-Laplace distributions that refer to page ranks and access statistics are identified as existing content. Furthermore, the content addressed in the stochastic analysis offers different interdisciplinary links that are shown with the plastic waste example (e.g. organic chemistry in upper secondary schools, biology, ethics and philosophy with a neutral point of view example, ...) In the next step, the learning module will be optimized by teacher training students in a university course using DSR and it will be tested with children. The learning modules will be published as OER via Wikiversity.

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